

WIDE APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING SUBJECT FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN TEXTILE

Yesbosinova Nursulu Perdebayevna

Toshkent institute of textile and light industry
The department of Uzbek and foreign languages
nesbosinova197916@gmail.com

Annotation: *The article describes the features of teaching English to textile and light industry students for academic and professional purposes. Provides detailed information on the language skills and abilities required to develop in the learning process.*

Аннотация: *маколада туқмачилик ва енгил саноат талабаларга илмий ва касбий мақсадлар учун инглиз тилини ўқитишнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари тасвирланган. Ўқитиш жараёнида ривожлантириш учун зарур булган тил куникмалари ва қобилиятлари ҳақида батафсил маълумот берилди.*

Калит сузлар: *чет тили, туқмачилик институти, ваколат, мулоқот, куникмалар ва қобилиятлар.*

- The successful professionalization of the teacher of the Institute of Higher Education is characterized by readiness for collegial work, the ability to maintain
- internal motivation at a high level, the development of innovative types and forms
- of work, the awareness of the need for constant professional and creative growth
- in accordance with the new conditions.

Pedagogical technologies to the educational process is a unique innovative approach. It is social in pedagogy expression of engineering thinking, education, training by putting the side in a certain standard state, its optimal when it is a concept related to creating a project, learning with the help of computers, technical means of

education, manager, organizer of the student’s cognitive activity, the advisor, the guide to achieve the final result that is the possibility of achieving the result.

The listener has the purpose of every lesson. It is necessary to determine the standards of motivation corresponding to the content. In pedagogy there are different ways to interest students in the lesson.

One of the effective methods is a Situational task. A teacher offers to the students at the beginning of the training a special problem assignments that can express the topic. A Situational task (problem) expresses concrete or abstract understanding and solves it to find new knowledge, new methods and actions.

*Use of research methods **Brainstorming**.* The essence of the "Brainstorming" method is the basis of team cooperation problem-solving processes in several steps (compilation of ideas and constructive state development) consists of separation. First, the group is assembled and a problem is set before them. All participants agree on the solution to this problem express their opinions. The main thing is understood in the process of solving the problem from the atmosphere of struggle to the mood of creative cooperation.

Mind map. Great tool to work out as many ideas as you can in hierarchical tree and cluster format. Staff off with your goal in the center, branch out into the major

sub-topics, continue to branch out into as many sub-sub-topics as needed. Source Forge is a great open-source mindmapping software that we use and highly recommend. **Cluster.** History of cluster (English cluster- cluster, brush, swarm) – the union of several homogenous elements, which can be considered as an independent unit with certain properties. In information technology

Cluster as a subset of search results related to the topic's unity;

In linguistics:

Cluster (linguistics)- a group of closely related languages or dialects

Sequence, a chain of language elements that can be sounds (vocal cluster) or parts of speak an educational role-playing game is also used to solve problems and increase motivation. Role-playing games can be carried out in the process of studying a separate topic. Topics such as "Parts of the textile", "examination", "Administering medication", "Case history", etc. (verbal cluster) The project method is another method that is one of the most effective methods of active learning in independent work of students. Working on a project is a creative process, as it requires a lot of attention. Students independently or with the help of a teacher search and select the necessary information for the presentation, i.e. learn to navigate in the information space. Students become active participants, and the teacher guides their activities and helps them. Students can submit the project in the form of computer presentations, essays, abstracts.

Thus active methods are aimed at creating a favorable motivational and emotional background in a foreign language lesson, which leads to the development of a sustainable interest in mastering it. In conclusion I want to say that it is the teacher who should help the student overcome the difficulties of learning a foreign language and by all means motivate and prepare the student for its correct perception as an important discipline and we were convinced of this in our classes on the subject of Foreign Language in Textile.

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